

DEPLOYMENT AND INTEGRATION OF MATOMO WEB ANALYTICS FOR CERN WEB SERVICES

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PROJECT SPECIFICATION

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The Web Frameworks section of the IT-CDA group provides services around Web content and application publishing, and software development tools for version control and issue tracking. Within this context, the CERN Web Services presently host about 14000 Websites on a heterogeneous infrastructure of more than 150 Web servers, including Drupal, SharePoint, Windows IIS, Linux Apache, TWiki, and OpenShift.

The student will work with cutting-edge web technologies to deploy the Web Analytics solution [Matomo](#) for CERN's centrally managed Web sites. With this solution we aim to cover both the Web server logs analytics and a JavaScript client, currently based on the CERN developed Log Dispatcher application and Piwik.

This project includes the deployment of this open-source project in our software container OpenShift service, the design and development of maintenance and operation processes, and the integration with the CERN Web Frameworks portal (<https://cern.ch/web-frameworks>).

ABSTRACT

To provide a scalable web analytics solution for the approximately 14000 websites hosted by CERN Web Services we deployed Matomo Web Analytics on CERN's OpenShift container platform. In order to integrate Matomo with the existing infrastructure we developed a custom plugin providing user authentication and management based on Shibboleth. Furthermore, we developed a controller exploiting information in OpenShift routes for automatic user and access management using the Go programming language. Finally, we created project documentation and future work proposals as a reference for future project members.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Roughly 14000 websites are hosted by CERN Web Services by the time of this writing and web analytics are an invaluable tool for evaluation and improvement of these services for the respective website owners. As website traffic is steadily growing it becomes increasingly challenging to serve the resulting demands for availability and scalability. The deployment of Matomo Web Analytics on CERN's OpenShift Container Platform tackles these issues and was realized in this project. In the following we give an overview of the designed solution and its core concepts.

As can be seen in Figure 1 the application is deployed on CERN's OpenShift Container Platform. Residing in two separate Kubernetes Pods the application is split into two parts, firstly the actual Matomo application secured by Shibboleth Single Sign-On and secondly an access controller managing administration privileges for website specific web analytics in Matomo.

Figure 1: General Application Scheme

The Matomo application pod hosts the Matomo application on top of an Apache web server as well as a Shibboleth daemon, both running in separate Docker containers based on the same base image. The Shibboleth daemon authenticates external (outside the OpenShift platform) user requests and passes them on to Matomo if applicable. Matomo in turn employs a custom login plugin ('*LoginCERN*') to manage user accounts based on Shibboleth user authentication information. An OpenShift route exposes the Matomo application pod to external requests as host '*NAMESPACE.web.cern.ch*' listening on port 8080 where the namespace is either '*test-matomo*' for development or '*matomo*' for production.

A separate pod hosts the Matomo Access Controller, again running inside a Docker container. This controller manages user accounts and website administration permissions in the context of Matomo based on OpenShift route information for websites hosted on OpenShift. The controller uses the Matomo API sending HTTP requests over a cluster internal OpenShift service connecting controller and application pods.

The remainder of this report is structured as follows. [Section 2](#) gives more information on the Matomo application as well as the custom login plugin. Section 3 explains in more detail the Matomo Access Controller and its connection to Matomo. In Section 4 typical deployment processes for the application are described whereas in Section 5 concludes the project and gives an outline and recommendations for future work. Finally, Section 6 gives a compact list of technologies used in the course of this project.

2. MATOMO WEB ANALYTICS ON OPENSHIFT

This section describes the installation and update processes for Matomo and explains the authentication mechanisms implemented by the developed custom login plugin in more detail.

a. Installation

To install Matomo from scratch (mainly in order to create a new database) one first has to make sure, that the configuration file *config.ini.php* used by Matomo does not exist inside the deployed container. This can be achieved by deleting the file via remote shell or OpenShift Web Interface terminal. Calling the Matomo service 'https://NAMESPACE.web.cern.ch' in any web browser will redirect to the installation screen where one can simply follow the [installation guide](#). If, for any reason, there already exists a database which is no longer of any use, one can delete it using any MySQL client (e.g. phpMyAdmin, etc.) manually. Finally, the configuration file *config.ini.php* should be created according to the user's requirements and included in the proper directory to ensure the expected behaviour.

b. Updating Matomo

[Updating Matomo](#) to a newer version can simply be done by altering the 'MATOMO_VERSION' environment variable inside the respective *Dockerfile*. Find the available Matomo builds [here](#). After changing the version in the *Dockerfile* the project must be re-build and re-deployed. Finally, Matomo ('https://NAMESPACE.web.cern.ch') must be called in a web browser in case structural changes to the database are necessary. Matomo will then prompt any super user to do so.

c. LoginCERN – A Custom Login Plugin for Matomo

Since at the time of this project there is no free and appropriate Single-Sign On/Authentication Plugin for Matomo available this custom plugin has been developed. There are two authentication use cases covered by this plugin:

i. Shibboleth Authentication for Website Requests

Important: The LoginCERN plugin does not implement the Shibboleth authentication routines itself! Therefore, using the plugin without access to Matomo being restricted by a separate Shibboleth daemon and the proper Apache web server configuration will potentially grant full access to all Matomo resources to any user!

In case the Matomo virtual host is secured by Shibboleth, the plugin uses the Shibboleth authentication information in the global PHP `$_SERVER` array. If a user requests any Matomo resource, the plugin checks if the user given the information in `$_SERVER` already exists in Matomo's database. If so, it the access is simply granted according to the existing user's access rights. If the user does not exist in the database, a new user is created, and by default no access rights are granted at all.

As of now, the plugin is configurable by the following parameters which can either be set in the configuration file `config.ini.php` via OpenShift ConfigMap or directly via Matomo's web interface (for super users only):

- **logout_url:** Matomo redirects to this URL after logging out the user
- **shibboleth_user_login:** The value in `$_SERVER['shibboleth_user_login']` represents the Matomo user name
- **shibboleth_user_alias:** The value in `$_SERVER['shibboleth_user_alias']` represents the Matomo user alias
- **shibboleth_user_email:** The value in `$_SERVER['shibboleth_user_email']` represents the Matomo user's email
- **shibboleth_group:** The values in `$_SERVER['shibboleth_group']` represents the users group memberships
- **shibboleth_separator:** The separator used to separate groups in the `$_SERVER['shibboleth_group']` and **shibboleth_superuser_groups** strings.
- **shibboleth_superuser_groups:** User groups that are granted super user access to Matomo. This parameter is optional.

ii. API Request Authentication via Token

Important: To authenticate any API request via token, the target virtual host must **not** be secured by Shibboleth, since otherwise the API request will never reach Matomo in this case but will be rejected by Shibboleth beforehand.

To provide the possibility for API requests from inside the OpenShift cluster two components have been introduced:

- An Apache virtual host serving Matomo configured to listen to port 8081
- A [headless](#) OpenShift service that makes the Matomo pod available under `'matomo-api.NAMESPACE.svc:8081'` inside the OpenShift cluster where `NAMESPACE` refers to the OpenShift project namespace.

To [authenticate API requests via token](#), the token send with the request must belong to an existing Matomo user with sufficient (super user) access permissions. For more information on the how the Matomo API is currently used in the project refer to Section [3.c. Communication with Matomo](#).

3. MATOMO ACCESS CONTROLLER

This section describes the [Golang](#) controller managing access rights to the Matomo Web Analytics deployment based on website ownership information present in OpenShift. Administrator privileges in Matomo are granted for the website identified by the `host` - annotation to the user identified by the `owner` - annotation of that website. **Important:** the website must be created in Matomo (manually) beforehand **and** the route's `host` - annotation must match the site's host in the Matomo database! Otherwise, the controller will simply ignore the given OpenShift route.

a. Controller Business Logic

The controller runs in a single worker thread. It fetches OpenShift routes in a given namespace and synchronizes them with its internal list of synchronized routes. The synchronization process follows the following logic.

- If a route has no document root, no owner or if it is blocked, then
 - an already synchronized route is deleted and respective access rights are revoked.
 - any non-synchronized route is simply ignored.

- If a route has all necessary annotations and it is not already synchronized, then the route owner is granted administrator privileges to the site connected to the route's host. If the site owner does not exist in the Matomo database, a new user account is created automatically.
- If a route is already synchronized and its owner changes, then the respective access rights for the old owner are revoked and the new route owner is granted administrator privileges to the site connected to the route's host.

In case any errors may occur during any synchronization process, the synchronization state of the respective route is left unchanged.

b. Communication with Matomo

In order to modify user and site access information in Matomo's database the controller uses Matomo's [Reporting HTTP API](#). API requests are send using plain HTTP over a cluster internal service (not visible outside the OpenShift cluster) that makes the Matomo application pod reachable `'matomo-api.NAMESPACE.svc:8081'`. However, Matomo requires an authentication token in order to use API requests. Thus, a service account with super user privileges must be created in Matomo (manually) and the corresponding authentication token is stored as a secret in the respective GitLab project. This secret is then provisioned to the controller pod at deployment time.

4. DEPLOYMENT ON THE OPENSIFT CONTAINER PLATFORM

Currently, there are two ways of deploying Matomo on OpenShift.

- **Deployment from scratch using YAML templates:**
To create all required resources and to deploy Matomo on OpenShift in a clean way using the [OpenShift CLI](#) one must carry out the following steps:
 1. Install the OpenShift CLI and connect to the OpenShift Cluster
 2. Get a local copy of the YAML templates for the project
 3. (Optional) Delete any resources (routes, services...) connected with the existing Matomo deployment
 4. Delete any existing OpenShift ConfigMaps
 5. Create resources and deploy Matomo with the necessary credentials using the YAML templates
- **GitLab CI/CD Pipeline**

Once an initial deployment exists, build and deployment are handled by the GitLab CI/CD Pipeline.

5. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

As of now, Matomo is deployed on CERN's OpenShift development environment. In order to solve the challenges arising during the integration process a custom login plugin for Matomo as well as a Golang controller for access management was developed. Finally, project documentation was created in order to provide a starting point for future project members.

Before the project can eventually be deployed on the OpenShift production environment, some work is left to do which is outlined in the following non-exhaustive list.

- The GitLab CI/CD pipelines should further be automatized and simplified by using the [Helm](#) package manager for Kubernetes. Moreover, integration tests have to be defined in the pipeline.
- Matomo provides two standard ways of gathering information for web analytics, either by using a [JavaScript Tracking Client](#) or web server [Log Analytics](#). Both possibilities must be evaluated in terms of provided features, applicability and usefulness. Based thereon, workflows for simple project integration for website owners have to be designed and implemented.
- Extensive scalability and performance tests must be set up in order to serve up to 14000 websites in production.
- [Optional]: In the long term, it is advisable to replace the developed login plugin by an appropriate commercial plugin (e.g. [LoginSAML](#)). This would avoid maintenance issues as Matomo evolves over time and mitigate restrictions and application complexity imposed by the current Shibboleth workaround.

After completing these next steps, the application can finally be deployed in the OpenShift production environment and enable website owners at CERN to improve their services using Matomo.

6. TECHNOLOGIES

The following is a compact (and non-exhaustive) list of technologies used in the course of this project:

- Matomo Web Analytics: <https://matomo.org/>
- RedHat OpenShift: <https://www.openshift.com/>

- Kubernetes: <https://kubernetes.io/>
- Docker: <https://www.docker.com/>
- GitLab (CI/CD): <https://about.gitlab.com/>
- GoLang: <https://golang.org/>
- PHP: <http://php.net/>
- Apache Webserver: <https://httpd.apache.org/>
- Shibboleth: <https://www.shibboleth.net/>

